

ESiWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #7 / February 2025

News

Open Call for Proposals to Advance Europe's Weather and Climate Models for Pre-Exascale Systems

The ESiWACE3 Consortium is excited to announce an open call for proposals: “Collaborations to prepare Europe’s Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale Systems.”

This service offers collaborative projects in which ESiWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant. This call aims to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth-System Models (ESM) community

With this service, the ESiWACE3 Consortium establishes collaborative projects in which the ESiWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant. Apart from offering limited engineering time and implementing code modifications, the projects aim to provide guidance and establish knowledge transfer between HPC experts and modelling groups.

The call is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM codes, not only the ESiWACE3 partners. It will run from 13 January 2025 until 3 March 2025 at 14:00 h CET. Proposals will be subject to review regarding technical feasibility by the service-providing partners and undergo a review more focussed on scientific impact by an external committee. When found eligible, the project will be granted an in-kind contribution by one of the partners (or a combination thereof).

For more information, including the full call description and guidelines, download the detailed document [here](#). Applications can be submitted via our [online form](#).

esiwace
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

CALL FOR PROPOSALS: MODEL OPTIMISATION, ACCELERATION and HPC EXPLOITATION

We offer to collaborate with developers of weather and climate models to improve model efficiency and readying the software to enable model execution on existing and near-future hardware architectures

“Collaborations to prepare Europe’s Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale Systems”
This service offers collaborative projects in which ESIWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant.

This call aims to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth-System Models (ESM) community.

DEADLINE:
3 March 2025 at
14:00 h CET

More information
<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/esiwace3-call-for-proposals-s1>

Co-funded by the European Union

ESIWACE3, NCC Austria and MultiXscale CoE training

ESIWACE3 and the National Competence Center for HPC in Austria organized the training event "Extrae and Paraver: Profiling Weather and Climate Applications" as part of the CASTIEL2 Training Sprint on January 27, 2025.

The course, attended by around 40 participants, focused on the BSC performance analysis tools, which are a set of different tools to support developers in the evaluation, tuning, and optimization of their codes.

In collaboration with the MultiXscale Centre of Excellence, the training also introduced the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI). EESSI consists of a shared stack of scientific software installations to provide a uniform user experience with respect to available scientific software, regardless of which system they use.

The course consisted of a theoretical part and hands-on labs for participants to practice how to analyze an Extrae trace with Paraver. They used a climate application as a demonstration, focusing on typical problems arising from numerical models and computational fluid dynamic applications while using EESSI to run all of them.

ESiWACE3 at the HiPEAC25 conference

Between the 20th and 22nd of January, [HiPEAC25](#) took place in Barcelona and ESiWACE3 was present in various formats. After two decades of connecting and inspiring the HPC community, HiPEAC returned to Barcelona for its 20th edition.

To start with, ESiWACE3, together with the European Centres of Excellence (CoEs), hosted two special workshops to delve into the world of HPC. These workshops also celebrated the contributions of women experts in the field. These workshops brought together a wide range of experts from different projects, with representatives from all the CoEs and relevant Euro-HPC initiatives.

Caption: Sophie Valcke from CERFACS

During these workshops, we counted with the presence of our invited guests Jenni Kontkanen from [CSC – IT Center for Science](#), Development Manager of the European project Digital Twins, who about Building Digital Twins of Earth on EuroHPC supercomputers, and Sophie Valcke from [CERFACS](#) and former co-leader of the WP6 of ESiWACE2, who talked about Carbon Footprint of CMIP simulations.

Caption: Round table with Thaleia Doudali, Madeleine Gray, Rosa María Badia, Alan O’Cais, Arnau Folch and Mario Acosta

Furthermore, our ESIWACE3 scientist Maitane Fariñas from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center explained Mixed Precision in Earth System models and Mario Acosta from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Principal Investigator of ESIWACE3, was part in the round table in Women, HPC and CoEs: HPC challenges for the Future.

All in all, ESIWACE3 was well represented at HiPEAC25, creating new collaborations and increasing our interactions within the HPC community.

New Online Laboratory for Data Compression

As part of the ESIWACE3 Centre of Excellence, our researchers have developed the second public version of the Online Laboratory for Data Compression tailored to climate science and meteorology. This initiative is complemented by the release of specialised datasets designed to test various compression methods on outputs from both weather and climate models.

The laboratory includes a collection of Jupyter notebooks that allow users to:

- Explore datasets for medium-range weather predictions and climate simulations.
- Apply both lossless and lossy compression techniques through an intuitive API.
- Perform diagnostics to evaluate potential degradations in the information content of data resulting from lossy compression.

Additionally, the platform provides the more broadly-applicable Online Laboratory as a Service, enabling users to access and utilize the compression tools or run arbitrary Python code without the need for local installation or setup, as popular earth science Python packages come pre-installed. Users can seamlessly work with datasets generated from prominent models, including the IFS, OpenIFS, and ICON models, which are available for exploration within the laboratory or for direct download via an S3 bucket.

You can find the Online Laboratory here:

- Our GitHub organization: <https://github.com/climet-eu>

- The online laboratory: <https://lab.climet.eu/>
- The compression laboratory: <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/>

Introducing Our New ESiWACE3 Animation Video!

We are delighted to announce the release of our brand-new animation video, showcasing the third phase of the European Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate Simulation (ESiWACE3). This video highlights our journey and the milestones we have achieved so far.

This engaging video, produced with our partner Latest Thinking, provides a comprehensive overview of our key pillars to the HPC community: support, development of tools and methods, training, and a hub for collaboration. It makes it easier than ever to understand the impact and significance of our work.

We invite you to view and share the animated video.

Capture: video animation thumbnail

ESiWACE3 celebrates its 3rd General Assembly

The 3rd General Assembly of the 3rd phase of the European Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate Simulations was organized in person by the leading institution, the Barcelona Supercomputing Center-Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS), and hosted by our partners, Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ).

All ESIWACE3 consortium at the General Assembly in Hamburg

The general assembly was inaugurated by Mario Acosta, the principal investigator (PI) of ESIWACE3, who welcomed all the partners and summarized the general state of ESIWACE3. He highlighted the strong presence of the Centre of Excellence at several conferences and workshops, as well as its increased impact on social media. Furthermore, on the morning of November 12th, the Consortium reviewed the project status by listening to summaries of the work performed over the last year within each Work Package.

Following this, we had the honour of hosting Irina Sandu, the Director of Destination Earth (DestinE) at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), who gave an external talk to reinforce the collaboration between ESIWACE3 and the promising Destination Earth project.

Mario Acosta's wrap up and farewell

Then, the next morning, 13 November 2024, after the Work Package Focus Group and the Flagship presentations, the Management Team invited several external speakers to present and elaborate on some initiatives of potential interest to the Consortium. First, Claudia Frauen (DKRZ) presented the WarmWorld project, ESIWACE3's partner in the organisation of the Summer Schools. Then, Hendryk

Bockelmann (DKRZ) explained the German national project natESM and its relation to ESIWACE3. Next, Torben König (SMHI) talked about Optim-ESM as a potential stakeholder to invite and push for collaboration. Thomas Jung from AWI then presented the EERIE project and finally, the HiDALGO2 Centre of Excellence was presented by its PI, Marcin Lawenda.

Last, but not least, Mario Acosta closed the event by describing the next steps of ESIWACE3 and the exciting future the CoE has in store.

Events

External events

External events in which ESIWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESIWACE Newsletter:

- [National Hydrological and Climate Modeling Seminar](#), Helsinki (Finland), 20 November 2024. [Talk](#)
- [Hidalgo2 - Hackathon on Atmosphere-Fire interaction](#), Madrid (Spain), 2 December 2024. [Talk](#)
- [ChEEsE Workshop](#), Online, 10 December 2024. [Talk](#)
- [HiPEAC Conference](#), 20-22 February 2024. Round table. Organization. Booth

Updates

Deliverables:

Deliverable 2.1 Report on the tool development for an automated reduction in precision

This deliverable summarises the work performed on the reduction of numerical precision in weather and climate applications, with a focus on the NEMO ocean model and the new finite volume dynamical core developed at ECMWF – the IFS-FVM. This work has been carried out by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) as part of Task 2.1 of ESIWACE3.

Read D2.1 [here](#).

Deliverable 2.3 Report on DSL development in NEMO and IFS-FVM

This deliverable shows the enhancements made so far on DSL development in NEMO and IFS-FVM models with the aim of allowing the targeting of these models on GPUs. In particular, the document summarizes the progress made when PSyclone DSL in NEMO and GT4Py DSL in IFS-FVM are used.

Read D2.3 [here](#).

Deliverable 3.3 Report on the online version of the data sets

This deliverable documents the development of an Online Laboratory for Data Compression in Climate Science and Meteorology and the publication of the data compression datasets that allow the testing of various compression methods for output of both weather and climate models.

Read D3.3 [here](#).

Deliverable 3.5 Report on domain- specific FDO standard

This deliverable report outlines the implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Digital Objects (FDOs) to enhance climate data management by improving data findability and interoperability. Together, FDOs, DTRs, and IPFS form a robust, FAIR-aligned framework, designed to meet the demands of climate research and promote cross-disciplinary data sharing.

Read D3.5 [here](#).

Deliverable 5.1 Report on the first summer schools

This report describes the organisation and feedback from the first ESIWACE3 summer school on “Effective HPC for weather and climate modellers”. The related teaching material will be published on the ESIWACE website <https://www.esiwace.eu/>. The summer school was organised late August 2024 in Espoo, Finland and was targeted at advanced MSc students and PhD students and postdoctoral researchers in Earth system sciences. The objectives were to train young scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use HPC environments in their research, and to support students in building their network. Overall feedback from the participants was positive and generally, a favorable appraisal was given.

Read D5.1 [here](#).

Deliverable 7.3 Update of data management plan

This deliverable is the second version of the Data Management Plan of the project. It is the revision of D7.2 submitted in June 2023 where the initial plan was set up. It will be revised at Month 47 (D7.4 -Final update of data management plan).

Read D7.3 [here](#).

Milestones:

Milestone 2.1 Version 1 of reduced precision tools are available for download and use

AutoRPE is a tool designed to help with the optimization of the numerical precision of Computational Science models written in Fortran. As part of this milestone, the AutoRPE repository has been made publicly accessible at earth.bsc.es/gitlab/ces/hpc-for-es-team/AutoRPE, ensuring transparency and fostering collaboration

Read M2.1 [here](#).

Milestone 3.3 Datasets and compression methods contained in Jupyter notebooks are available online to allow for compression evaluations

This milestone documents the publication of an Online Laboratory for Data Compression in Climate Science and Meteorology that allows the testing of various compression methods for output of both weather and climate models. The Jupyter notebooks of the compression laboratory explore several

datasets for ensemble weather predictions and climate simulations, apply lossy compression techniques in an easy-to-use way, and allow to perform a number of diagnostics to evaluate possible degradations due to compression. We also provide an online laboratory as a service, which hosts the compression laboratory notebooks and allows users to quickly jump in and explore compression without needing to install or setup anything. A detailed description of the data and tools can be found in deliverable D3.3 that is published alongside this milestone document.

Read M3.3 [here](#).

News from the neighbours

Upcoming conferences and events

- [EuroHPC Summit 2025](#), 18-20 March 2025, Kraków (Poland)
- [EGU General Assembly 2025](#), 27 April to 2 May 2025, Vienna (Austria) & Online
- [ISC High Performance 2025](#), 10-13 June 2025, Hamburg (Germany)

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).